

**UNFOLDING THE PHARMACOGNOSY OF NIGHT JASMINE
(*NYCTANTHESARBOR-TRISTIS*): A TRADITIONAL HEALER IN NEW
ERA**

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ABSTRACT

The Parijat flower, also known as Harsingar or Night-blooming Jasmine (*Nyctanthes arbor tristis*), occupies an important place in the ancient Ayurvedic text and also in other traditional systems of medicine, while being enwrapped by years of cultural and spiritual legacy. Each part of the plant shows distinct therapeutic potentials, which strongly justify an all-comprehensive use in evidence-based medicinal applications. In this review, we study the historical contribution, phytochemical properties, and medical applications of Harsingar and try to establish its relevance in holistic healing practices. It unites the ancient with the modern para-scientific work in an attempt to identify the broad pharmacological activities that it possesses and the bioactive compounds that lie therein, as well as the newer application areas in modern health care. Bioactive chemical constituents, including flavonoids, glycosides, and alkaloids, have been reported, validating some

of the therapeutic potentials of night flowering jasmine. It provides traditional and scientific insights into the role of harsingar in managing diseases and promoting wellness.

KEYWORDS: Parijat, *Nyctanthesarbor-tristis* L., Anti-Inflammatory, Phytochemistry.

INTRODUCTION

The *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* Linn. plant is found in medicinal applications across India. It belongs to the Oleaceae family, is popularly known as "Parijat", "Night jasmine" and "Harsingar". The Greek word arbor-tristis means "sad tree", with respect to shedding brightness only during the day, whereas the term nyctanthes means "night flower".^[1] Parijata derives its name from "Paarinaha Samudrath jaatho va parijat": Its genesis in the Samudra (Ocean) as a result of (parinaha) exhaustive seeking is why it is called Parijata.^[2] It is one of the ethno-medicinal herbs traditionally known in Asia and in India. It is native to India and stretches to the south of the Godavari River and down below the Himalayas. Alternative medical systems like Ayurveda, Sidha, and Unani use the leaves, flowers, bark, fruit, and seeds of the plant since they all embody unique pharmacological properties.^[3] The whole plant is used as an herbal remedy for blood purification, splenic enlargement, arthritis, malaria, chronic fever, rheumatism, and internal worm infections, and as a laxative, diaphoretic, diuretic and for sciatica, whereas the parts are separately applied.^[4] These are very common shrubs or trees and grow wild across their habitat range. Scientific studies have proven the many traditional uses attributed to it. The present review shall elucidate the full account of the pharmacological activities and chemical components of this plant. From Nepal to Chenab, Burma Assam, Central India, Bengal, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattanagpur, and south to the Godavari, *N. arbor-tristis* is a sub-Himalayan plant that grows wild.^[1] Traditional medicines still form an important part of global healthcare, with about 75% of the world relying on plants and plant-derived compounds for treatment and wellness. among which Indian medicinal flora are particularly rich in diverse phytochemicals showing a wide range of pharmacological activities. Conventional anti-inflammatory agents, such as opioids and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, although effective, often show adverse effects such as redness and itching, thus necessitating the development of safer alternatives derived from plants. The growing scientific literature cites innumerable plants from all sections of botany that show excellent anti-inflammatory properties largely due to the flavonoid constituents present in them. Major examples of these plants include *Acacia nilotica*, *Withania somnifera*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Boswellia serrata*, *Phyllanthus amarus*, *Eclipta alba*, and *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*. Amongst them, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* is particularly distinguished by the presence of a very high abundance of flavonoids and other bioactive compounds, rendering it a viable candidate for anti-inflammatory therapy research and therapeutics.^[5]

Fig. 1: Plant of N. Arbortristis.

Taxonomical classification

Binomial name: *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*

Kingdom: Plantae

Division: Magnoliophyta Class: Magnoliopsida Order: Lamiales

Family: Oleaceae Genus: Nyctanthes

Species: Arbortristis^[1,6]

Synonyms of plant in different languages

Latin: *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*

Hindi: Harsingar, Parijat, Raatki Rani.

Sanskrit: Sephalika, Vatari, Shuklangi, Shefalika, Aparajtha, Vijaya. English: Night jasmine, Weeping nyctanthas, Tree of sorrow.

Bangali: Shefalika, Shivuli. Gujarati: Harshanagar.

Kannada: Parijatha. Marathi: Parijath. Telugu: Parijatamu. Tamil: Majjapu^[7,8]

It is used in various parts of India for the Management of various clinical disorders. The paste of leaves of this plant is applied in cases of pain and swelling in the joints. The powdered bark and leaves are mixed and applied to the affected part, tied with a cloth, and found effective in fractures and wound healing. The seed paste is applied to the scalp to treat dandruff. Keeping the wood of Parijat wrapped in red cloth in a purse, vault, or near money is believed to ensure that money remains sufficient, in accordance with ancient Indian spiritual and Vastu practices. Although there is no scientific verification, it holds cultural significance and religious connotation **Error! Bookmark not defined.**

MORPHOLOGY

- Seeds: The fruits are broad, elongated capsules that can be obcordate or almost spherical in shape, with a diameter of 1-2 cm. They have reticulated veins, are smooth (glabrous), compressed, and have two cells. The outer layer is composed of large, translucent cells and is highly vascularized. The seeds have a thick seed coat known as testa and are exalbuminous, meaning they lack endosperm.^[1]
- The bark and stem: This big bush can reach a height of ten meters. The brown to dark grey bark of the *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* gives it a mature, robust appearance.^[2,7]
- Leaves: A few broad, far-off spikes accentuate the short, puffy hairs that adorn the long, acute, or pointed leaves, making them tough and slightly hairy. They are at total opposites with one another. They measure 6–12 cm in length and 2–6 cm in width and have an ovate lamina with a sharp or pointed apex. Its margins may be smooth or serrated, gradationally sinuous close to the base. The petiole is 6 cm long, with silky hairs. Each leaf is attached to the branch by slender petioles; the upper side is dark green, while the underside is light.^[9,10]
- Fruits: Each fruit is a flat, brown, two-lobed capsule approximately 2 cm in diameter as well as spherical or heart-shaped. They are obcordate, solid, and have two cells that split into two equal carpels from one seed. The surface of these fruits is smooth with a reticulate vein pattern.^[9]
- Flowers: The Harsingar plant bears miniature, fragrant, sessile flowers with white lobed petals and an orange-red corolla tube, borne in clusters of three to five. Four-angled, slender, hairy pedicels in small terminal cymes support them. The plant is popularly called the Night Jasmine, due to its delicate flowers, which bloom at night.^[10]

Fig No. 2: Leaf of N. Arbortristis.

Fig No. 3: Fruit of N. Arborescens.

Fig No. 4 Bark of N. Arborescens.

Fig. No. 5: Seeds of N. Arborescens.

Fig No. 6: Flower of N. Arborescens.

Table No. 1: Various parts of plant including its therapeutic uses, chemical constituents and activity.

Part	Therapeutic uses	Chemical constituents	Activity	Structure
1. Leaves	Expectorant, blood disorders Anti-inflammatory, tonifying Inducing perspiration Clearing constipation Febrile illnesses (intermittent/chronic) Intestinal worms (children) Skin disorders (ringworm, eczema) Dry cough (children) Excess mucus (bark + betel nut) Women' s ailments Snake venom antidote Rheumatism, arthritis Error! Bookmark not defined. Error! Bookmark not defined. Error! Bookmark not defined. ,8,9	D-mannitol, β -sitosterol, Flavanol glycosides, Astragaline, Nicotiflorin, Oleanolic acid, Nyctanthic acid, Carotene, Friedeline, Lupeol, Mannitol, Glucose, Fructose, Iridoid glycosides, and benzoic acid. β -monogentiobioside ester of α -crocetin (or crocin-3), β -monogentiobioside, β -D monoglucoside ester of α -crocetin, β -digentiobioside ester of α -crocetin (or crocin-1), nyctanthin. ¹³	Detoxifying Anti-inflammatory Diaphoretic Laxative Antipyretic Anthelmintic Dermatological Respiratory support Mucolytic Gynecological Antidotal Joint pain relief	<p>Oleanolic acid</p>

2. Seeds	<p>Dermatological and antiparasitic properties Powdered seeds for dandruff and hair growth Powdered seeds with honey for malaria Decoction for gout Seed with water for hemorrhoids Seed paste for baldness Nutrient-rich seeds to prevent scurvy Error! Bookmark not defined.¹⁰</p>	<p>Seeds contain a variety of compounds, including arbortritoside A and B, glycerides of linoleic acid, oleic acid, lignoceric acid, stearic, palmitic, and Myristic acid, nycanthic acid, and 3-4 secotriterpene acid, a water-soluble polymer made up of Dglucose and Dmannose¹³</p>	<p>Dermatological Hair care Antimalarial Gout relief Hemorrhoid relief Baldness treatment Antiscorbutic</p>	<p>Arbortritoside B</p>
3. Flower	<p>Bitter and astringent properties Treatment of inflammation and related disorders Bathing with flowers for skin and hair Constipation relief in children Flower infusion for gout Vision, stomach, and gas support Relief from headache, vertigo, menstrual pain Treatment of fungal infections and bronchitis Error! Bookmark not defined.^{8,11,12}</p>	<p>Flower oil contains α-pinene, p-cymene, 1-hexanol methyl heptanone, phenyl acetaldehyde, 1-deconol, and anisaldehyde, 6-o-trans-cinnamoyl-7-o-acetyl-6β-hydroxyloganin, Arborside C, 6β-hydroxyloganin¹³.</p>	<p>Digestive aid Anti-inflammatory Skin care Laxative Gout relief Vision support Pain relief Antifungal</p>	<p>6β-hydroxyloganin</p>

4. Bark and stem	Traditional expectorant Relieves stomach inflammation and aids digestion Treats malaria Heals internal injuries and fractured joints ^{1,9}	The stem contains glycoside and β -sitosterol, naringenin-4-O- β -glucapyranosyl- α -xylopyranoside ¹³ .	Clears respiratory tract Digestive aid Antimalarial Wound healing	<p>Naringenin-4-O-β-glucapyranosyl-α-xylopyranoside</p>
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Fig. No. 7: Pharmacological activity of *N. Arbortristis*.^[2,14]

Pharmacological activities and Mechanism of action of *N. Arbortristis*:

1. Anticancer activity

The anticancer activities of *N. arbortristis* are reported for the first time in 2001. They demonstrated that the extracts of flowers in petroleum ether, chloroform, and ethyl acetate possess potent cytotoxicity. The methanol extract of the stem bark was shown to have more anticancer activity than 5-fluorouracil against Dalton's ascetic lymphoma in Swiss albino rats. Cytotoxicity was progressively increased by ethanol, methanol, and aqueous leaf extracts toward T-cell leukemia cells with greater time and higher doses. It reduced normal cell toxicity substantially with all dose levels and time periods tested.^[16,15,16,17]

Mechanism

- Activation of the caspase pathway
- Arrest of the cell cycle via flavonoids
- Inhibition of PI3K/AKT pathway.^[18]

2. Antimalarial activity

Antimalarial studies were done on 120 malaria patients, with the best clinical results being obtained when fresh paste from 5 medium-sized leaves of *N. arbortristis* was given 3 times daily for 7 days; 92 of the patients, or 76.7%, were considered cured as 20 patients in 10 days, while the other 8 could not be cured. Administration of paste was well tolerated, with no report of serious side effects.^[12,18,19,20,16,17]

Mechanism

- Modulation of liver detoxification enzymes *Plasmodium falciparum*
- Enhancement of immune clearance of the parasite
- Inhibition of pro-inflammatory cytokines.^[18]

3. Hepatoprotective activity

Ethanollic leaf extract of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* protects rats from carbon tetrachloride-induced toxic effects on the liver. In this experiment, seven days' pretreatment with the extract at a dosage of 1000 mg/kg body weight/day, p.o. was given to the rats before the administration of a single dose of CCl₄ at 1.0 ml/kg (s.c.). Blood was collected from the abdominal aorta from rats sacrificed under pentobarbitone anesthesia (350 mg/kg i.p.) after 48 hours of CCl₄ administration (9 days). Silymarin was used as the reference standard at a dose of 70 mg/kg body weight/day, p.o., for 7 days. In this study, *Nyctanthes arbortristis* leaf extract and silymarin both showed therapeutic activity in preventing body weight loss and preventing the increase in liver weight and volume due to CCl₄ and reversing all the serum and liver parameters changed by CCl₄ back to their normal levels.^[12,18,19,20,22,18]

Mechanism

- Protection from oxidative damage by neutralizing free radicals
- Inhibition of oxidative stress in liver cells
- Modulation of liver detoxification enzymes.^[18]

4. Anti-arthritic activity

The first sign of osteoarthritic pain at joints is a symptom of the slowly evolving, chronic degenerative arthritis arthritogenic activity on the joints and bones destruction. Most of the pathophysiology concerning rheumatoid arthritis has been attributed to the activity of various cytokines. The abnormal high expression of the tumor necrosis factor (TNF-) induced crippling

arthritis in experimental mice. The major arthritis had developed as inhibited in collagen-induced arthritis (CIA) because interleukin-1 (IL-1) was absent. The interleukin-6-knockout mice were resistant to collagens and antigen-induced arthritis. These studies give clear evidence for the contribution of the pro-inflammatory cytokines TNF, IL-1, and IL-6 to the disease process of rheumatoid arthritis-their justifiable rationale for intervention.^[2,12,16,18]

Mechanism

- Inhibition of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6)
- Inhibition of matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs)
- Modulation of immune responses.^[18]

Preparation and Uses

Almost every traditional system thinks of Parijat as a sacred plant, its findings are so extended. The extent of benefit for health promotion and the treatment of some common ailments by both external and internal application is exhibited by the different parts of the plant-the flowers, the leaves, and the bark and any of the extracts.

Herbal Teas and Infusions-Parijat flowers dried up are commonly brewed into a light, aromatic herbal tea. Applied in treating digestive complaints, relaxing the respiratory tract, soothing being carminative and expectorant, this age-old tea is concocted as an antidote to flatulence, coughs, and inflammatory conditions.

Topicals-Fresh leaves of Parijat are usually prepared in paste, or slightly warmed in mustard oil, to formulate topical applications for skin and joint condition remedies. The topical application of this agent is believed to alleviate skin infections and joint swelling and is therefore advocated in the management of disorders of the skin and musculoskeletal system.

Decoctions for Internal Use-A warm decoction of Parijat leaves or bark is usually ingested to lower fever, respiratory tract irritation, and digestive distress. Gargles are done with it in conditions affecting the mouth, such as ulcers, gum bleeding, and throat inflammation.

Extracts and Daily Supplements-Parijat is also available in powder or capsule form as a daily supplement. For chronic diseases, they are used as classical remedies for a long time, such as arthritis, respiratory, and liver disorders.

Essential Oils and Aromatherapy-Parijat flower essential oils help relieve stress and balance

emotions in the field of aromatherapy. These oils are very common in blends for muscle relaxation and find their place among perfumery for their moderate floral scent.^[10]

Commercial Applications

- *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* has significant implementations in traditional dyeing practices. The vivid orange corolla tubes of its flowers are embedded with saffron-like pigment known as nyctanthin, historically used for dyeing silk, employed alongside the safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius* L.), turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.), and indigo (*Indigofera* spp.).^[12] Locally, this dye is also used for coloring the robes of Buddhist monks and is applied to cotton fabrics and serves as an economical alternative. For dyeing, textiles are submerged in a decoction of the corolla tubes. While the dye imparts a vibrant orange, yellow, or golden hue, it tends to fade under sunlight and washing. To optimize color fastness, lime juice or alum is combined with the dye bath, enhancing resistance to light, soap, alkali, and acid.
- The bark may be employed as a tanning agent, and the leaves are seldom applied for polishing wood and ivory.
- Essential oils: The essential oil extracted from its fragrant flowers closely resembles jasmine oil and is traditionally utilized in perfumery.
- Timber and Wood Utilization: The timber of Parijat (*Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*) is moderately hard, brown, close-grained, and relatively dense (approximately 80 kg/m³). It is occasionally used for light construction purposes such as boarding and minor carpentry. The young, flexible branches are commonly employed in basket weaving, reflecting its utility in traditional crafts. In addition to these applications, the wood also serves as a source of firewood in rural areas. The plant is frequently cultivated as a hedge, providing an effective natural boundary, barrier, or structural support due to its dense growth habit.^[17]
- *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* has emerged as a promising botanical resource in nanoscience, with various plant extracts enabling the eco-friendly synthesis of nanoparticles. Its ethanolic flower extract is used to produce gold nanoparticles due to strong reducing properties, while silver nanoparticles derived from flower and seed extracts show cytotoxic and antibacterial effects against *E. coli*. Zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized

from floral extracts exhibit potent antifungal activity against species like *A. niger* and *B. cinerea*, and titanium oxide nanoparticles from leaf extracts are applied in biomedical and nanotech fields for their biocompatibility and photocatalytic traits. Collectively, NAT offers a sustainable platform for developing metal-based nanoparticles with diverse commercial applications.^[18]

Fig. No. 8: Efficacy and application of N. Arboortristisin Nanoscience.^[18]

CONCLUSION

Since the ancient times, this tree has had a place in Indian culture, folklore, and medicine. Its medicated properties, from leaves and flowers to seeds, bark, and roots, have attracted numerous pharmacological activities justifying its incorporation into the Ayurvedic, Siddha, and Unani systems of medicine. Dynamo in phytoconstituents, it encompasses flavonoids, glycosides, alkaloids, tannins, and essential oils. From several scientific studies, the traditional uses have been confirmed, including anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritic, antimalarial, anticancer, hepatoprotective, antioxidant, antidiabetic, antibacterial, antifilarial, and anti-anxiety actions. Its bioactive constituents, such as nyctanthin, arboortristosides, oleanolic acid, and β -sitosterol, have been studied for their potential against microbial infection, metabolic disorders, and chronic inflammatory diseases. New findings from mechanistic studies suggest its potential within the domains of cytokine modulation, oxidative stress inhibition, prevention of tissue damage, and regulation of immune responses.

Other uses for *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* include being a source of natural dyes, essential oils, and fragrance materials, and for this type of woodworking. The applications of this plant in cosmetics and aromatherapy, demonstrates its versatility in the healthcare sectors. Also, due to the tree's cultural importance in India, it is associated with holiness and is deemed pure and divine. Parijat is indeed a true alternative in the nature versus the synthetic medicine debate.

Modern biological sciences have contextualized the herb Parijat while allowing for the coexistence of allopathic medical paradigms with itself. It will thus form an overall ground to stand in for its entire medicinal potential by merging it with modern health care settings through future advances in complex multidisciplinary studies related to phytochemical analysis, mechanistic explanation, and clinical trials. Indeed, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* is today's sacred symbol of health which has 'proven to be a 'Herbal Panacea' scientifically.

REFERENCES

1. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
2. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
3. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
4. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
5. Londhe RM, Dhotre BG, Ahire AG, Jadhav SA, Falke AP. Review on formulation and evaluation of anti-inflammatory herbal gel. Int J Sci Innov Eng., 2025; 2(5): 161–9. doi:10.70849/ijsci.
6. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
7. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
8. Mishra P, Tiwari D, Tomar A, Verma A, Singhal S, Mittal J. Harsingar plant and its species: Review on medicinal uses, therapeutics effects and its importance. Advance Pharmaceutical Journal, 2022; 7(3): 67-72.
9. Meshram MM, Rangari SB, Kshirsagar SB, Gajbhiye S, Trivedi MR, Sahane RS. *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* a herbal panacea. International Journal of pharmaceutical sciences

- and research, 2012 Aug 1; 3(8): 2432.
10. Chauhan JS, A. New glycosides from *Nyctanthesarbortristis*. J Indian Chem Soc., 1978; 55: 1049–51
 11. Rahman A, Mosaddik A, Haque E. In vivo cytotoxic evaluation of a new benzofuran derivative isolated from *Nyctanthesarbor-tristis* L. on Ehrlich ascite carcinoma cells (EAC) in mice. J Med Sci (Faisalabad), 2003; 3(3): 169–73. doi:10.3923/jms.2003.169.173
 12. Bansal S, Bharati AJ, Bansal YK. In vitro callogenesis and phytochemical screening of harsingar (*Nyctanthesarbor-tristis*), a multipotent medicinal tree. Int J PharmTech Res., 2013; 5(4): 1786–93.
 13. Rawat H, Verma Y, Ayesha NS, Negi N, Pant HC, Mishra A, Singhal M, Khan A, Gaurav N. *Nyctanthesarbor-tristis*: a traditional herbal plant with miraculous potential in medicine. International Journal of botany Studies, 2021; 6: 427-40.
 14. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
 15. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
 16. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
 17. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.
 18. Kulkarni DM, Dhakne RB, Patil RR. Review of *Nyctanthes arbortristis* as a medicinal plant. Indian J Res Methods Pharm Sci., 2022; 1(2): 21–6. Available from: <https://www.ijrmps.com>.